

SYNTHESIS OF 5-METHOXY-2-INDANONE

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1-Bromo-3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-propan-2-one on treatment with anhydrous aluminium chloride affords *m*-methoxybenzylmethyl ketone. Ethyl *m*-methoxyphenylacetate, on chloromethylation, followed by oxidation, furnishes 4-methoxyphthalic and methoxyterephthalic acids. The cyano-esters, obtained from the above chloro-esters, are converted into a mixture of the crystalline diacetic acids (IV : R = R₁ = CH₂.CO₂H; R₂ = H and R = R₂ = CH₂.CO₂H; R₁ = H). *m*-Methoxybenzyl chloride on chloromethylation, followed by treatment with potassium cyanide and then hydrolysis, furnishes the same mixture of diacetic acids. The dimethyl esters of the latter, on cyclisation, afford an isomeric mixture of β-keto esters which are hydrolysed to the same indanone (II : R = R₁ = H).

With the object of synthesising the degradation and the dehydrogenation product of Jervine (cf. Chatterjee, Chatterjee and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 855) the preparation of 5-methoxy-2-indanone is reported below.

The cyclisation of 1-bromo-3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-propan-2-one (I : R = Br), prepared from *m*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride, diazomethane and hydrobromic acid, to the indanone (II : R = R₁ = H) by anhydrous aluminium chloride resulted in the formation of *m*-methoxybenzylmethyl ketone (I : R = H), identified by comparing its semicarbazone (m.p. 137-38°) with that of an authentic sample, prepared from *m*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride and diethyl malonate (Wilds and Close, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3079). Behal and Tiffeneau (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1908, iv, 3, 314) reported to have obtained the same ketone (I : R = H) by the action of mercuric oxide and iodine on *m*-methoxyphenylpropylene. The semicarbazone of their ketone has been described to melt at 175°. The failure to cyclise the bromoketone (I : R = Br) to the indanone (II : R = R₁ = H) is in agreement with the observation of Smith and Wilson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1342) who report that for the conversion of α-bromo-α'-phenylalkyl ketone into 2-indanone, the activation of bromine by a suitable α-substituent appears necessary.

Being unable to cyclise the above bromo-ketone in the expected way, experiments were modelled after Robinson and Crowley (*ibid.*, 1938, 2001; cf. Koo and Hartwell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1625), but, unfortunately, the cyclisation of ethyl α-formyl-β-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-propionate (III) under acidic conditions always resulted in a polymeric product. The desired indanone was finally prepared as described below.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

* In part.

The chloromethylation of ethyl *m*-methoxyphenylacetate yielded a mixture of chloro compounds (IV : $R = CH_2.CO_2Et$; $R_1 = CH_2Cl$; $R_2 = H$ and $R = CH_2.CO_2Et$; $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_2Cl$) in low yield. To establish the orientation of the chloromethyl group, the above mixture of the chloro compounds was oxidised to 4-methoxyphthalic and methoxyterephthalic acids. The mixture of the chloro-esters was converted into the corresponding cyano-esters which after esterification, followed by hydrolysis, furnished crystalline diacetic acids (IV : $R = R_1 = CH_2.CO_2H$; $R_2 = H$ and $R = R_2 = CH_2.CO_2H$; $R_1 = H$) ; but the chloromethylation of *m*-methoxybenzyl chloride, under controlled condition, afforded in moderately good yield a mixture of dichloro compounds (IV : $R = R_1 = CH_2Cl$; $R_2 = H$ and $R = R_2 = CH_2Cl$; $R_1 = H$) which was oxidised to the above phthalic acids. The above dichloro compounds were converted by the method of Moore and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 165) into a mixture of dinitriles, hydrolysis of which by acid or base furnished a poor yield of the aforementioned mixture of the diacetic acids ; but the conversion of the nitriles to the esters, followed by hydrolysis, afforded a better yield. The desired indanone (II : $R = R_1 = H$) was obtained in poor yield by heating the lead salts of the above mixture of the diacetic acids.

The separation of the diacetic acids to pure components was very difficult, but the sodioenolates of the β -keto esters (II : $R = H$; $R_1 = CO_2Me$ and $R = CO_2Me$; $R_1 = H$), produced by the Dieckmann cyclisation of the esters (IV : $R = R_1 = CH_2.CO_2Me$; $R_2 = H$ and $R = R_2 = CH_2.CO_2Me$; $R_1 = H$), may be easily separated from the unchanged ester (IV : $R = R_2 = CH_2.CO_2Me$; $R_1 = H$). With this end in view the mixture of dimethyl esters, obtained from the above diacetic acids, was subjected to the Dieckmann reaction to furnish sodioenolates, insoluble in benzene. The aqueous solution of the enolates on acidification furnished, probably, a mixture of isomeric β -keto esters (II : $R = CO_2Me$; $R_1 = H$ and $R = H$; $R_1 = CO_2Me$) which were separated by fractional crystallisation. Both the β -keto esters separately on hydrolysis afforded the same desired indanone (II : $R = R_1 = H$). The oxidation of one of the isomeric β -keto esters yielded 4-methoxyphthalic acid.

The attempted alkylation of one of the β -keto esters gave a mixture of products which could not be characterised. The Mannich-Robinson reaction with the indanone or with the β -keto esters was not promising, always yielding a polymerised product (Harradence and Lions, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1939, 72, 284; Wenkert and Bhattacharyya, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 797).

EXPERIMENTAL*

1-Bromo-3-(m-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-one (I : $R = Br$).—A mixture of *m*-methoxyphenylacetic acid (10 g.) in dry benzene (12 c.c.), pyridine (3 drops) and thionyl chloride (7.6 c.c.) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 3 hours, warmed at 40-50° for half an hour and distilled to furnish the acid chloride, b.p. 120°/2 mm, yield 6.8 g. To the dry ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (20 g.); cooled in a freezing mixture, was added the above acid chloride

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum was examined in 95% ethanol by the Unicam spectrophotometer, S.P. 500.

(4 g.), the mixture allowed to stand for 1 hour and then treated with hydrobromic acid (48%) till the evolution of nitrogen had ceased. After 16 hours at room temperature, the reaction mixture was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water, and dried over sodium sulphate. The residue, obtained after evaporation of the solvent, was evaporatively distilled at $130-40^{\circ}/2.5$ mm to furnish the bromo-ketone (2.4 g.). The analytical sample was evaporatively distilled at $130-35^{\circ}/2$ mm. (Found: Br, 32.31. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 32.92%). The bromo-ketone did not furnish a semicarbazone by the pyridine method.

Attempted Cyclisation of the Bromo-ketone (I: R=Br).—To a stirred anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.98 g) in tetrachloroethane (10 c.c.), cooled in an ice-bath, was added dropwise during half an hour a solution of the bromo-ketone (1.2 g.) in tetrachloroethane (3 c.c.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 16 hours and then it was decomposed by cold dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with dilute alkali, then water and dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at $75-85^{\circ}/1.5$ mm to furnish an oil (0.88 g.) which responded to the test for halogen. The oil was treated with semicarbazide hydrochloride in pyridine and methanol to furnish a semicarbazone (0.75 g.), m.p. $124-25^{\circ}$ which was refluxed for 6 hours with an aqueous solution of oxalic acid (35 c.c., 20%). The resulting oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium carbonate solution and water, and dried. The oily residue, after removal of the solvent, was evaporatively distilled at $70-80^{\circ}/1.5$ mm to afford *m*-methoxybenzylmethyl ketone in 0.4 g. yield. (Found: C, 73.16; H, 7.44. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 73.17; H, 7.31%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared from the above ketone (0.1 g.), was crystallised three times from dilute methanol, m.p. $137-38^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 59.82; H, 6.83; N, 19.02. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2$ requires C, 59.72; H, 6.78; N, 19.0%).

m-Methoxybenzylmethyl Ketone (I: R=H).—To sodio-malonic ester, prepared from sodium (1.4 g.) and diethyl malonate (14 g.) in ether (60 c.c.), was added with stirring *m*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride (1.02 g) at room temperature. The reaction mixture, after being kept standing for 16 hours, was acidified with cold dilute acetic acid. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted three times with a mixture of benzene and ether. The combined extract was washed with water and the oily residue, on removal of the solvent, was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.), HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) and water (12 c.c) for 2 hours. The cold reaction mixture was diluted with water and the precipitated oil was thoroughly extracted with ether-benzene mixture. The organic layer was washed with base and water, and dried. On removal of the solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at $70-80^{\circ}/1.5$ mm to yield a colorless ketone (0.8 g.). The *semicarbazone* of this ketone, m.p. $137-38^{\circ}$, prepared in the usual manner, did not depress the m.p. of the sample obtained above.

*Ethyl α -Formyl- β -(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-propionate* (III).—Ethyl β -(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-propionate was prepared in better yield in the following way

A mixture of *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde (27.2 g.), cyanoacetic ester (22.4 g.), ammonium acetate (8 g.), glacial acetic acid (9.6 c.c.) and benzene (400 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up to furnish a yellow oil (40 g.), b.p. 185-89°/2 mm which was then hydrogenated over palladium on charcoal catalyst (10%) in ethanol solution. The crude saturated cyano-ester (40 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with HCl (conc., 400 c.c.) for 40 hours and the crude acid, thus obtained, was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and alkali to furnish the pure crystalline acid (26 g.), b.p. 160°/1 mm, m.p. 45-46°; Johnson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2251) recorded m.p. 44-46°. The ethyl ester (22 g.), b.p. 135-40°/2.5 mm, was obtained by refluxing the acid (22 g.) with absolute ethanol (100 c.c.) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 6 c.c.).

To sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium dust (3.45 g.), absolute alcohol (8.6 c.c.) and benzene (60 c.c.), cooled in an ice-bath, was added with constant shaking a solution of the above ethyl ester (14.6 g.) and ethyl formate (12.9 c.c.) in dry ether (60 c.c.). The reaction mixture, after being kept standing for 48 hours at room temperature, was diluted with cold water. The aqueous layer was separated and extracted once with ether. The organic layers were combined and washed with 5% NaOH solution (cold and dilute). The unchanged propionic ester (5 g.) was obtained from the organic layer. The combined aqueous and alkaline solutions were acidified with HCl (cold and dilute) and saturated with ammonium chloride. The precipitated oil was extracted three times with ether and the ethereal layer was washed with water and dried. The residual oil, obtained after evaporation of the solvent, gave the formyl compound (8 g.), b.p. 135-40°/0.6 mm, which exhibited a strong violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 65.69; H, 7.05. C₁₁H₁₀O₄ requires C, 66.10; H, 6.77%).

Attempts were made to cyclise the above formyl compound in the following manners:

(i). To a mixture of phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 5 c.c.) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 1.3 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture, was added the formyl compound (1.4 g.). After 2 hours the reaction mixture was worked up to afford a polymerised product.

(ii). The attempted cyclisation of the formyl compound by heating at 240-50°/40 mm resulted in the isolation of the unchanged material.

(iii). The formyl compound was mixed with polyphosphoric acid (10 g.) at 0° and after 1 hour the reaction mixture was worked up to give a polymerised product.

(iv). The cold solution of the formyl compound (1 g.) in absolute methanol (20 c.c.) was saturated with dry HCl gas. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 16 hours in the refrigerator, refluxed for 6 hours and then worked up with ether to furnish an oil (0.18 g.), evaporatively distilling at 105-15°/1 mm; $\lambda_{\max}$ 307 m μ (log ϵ 3.96); but no crystalline acid could be obtained on treatment with base.

Ethyl 3-Methoxy-2-chloromethyl- and 3-Methoxy-4-chloromethyl-phenylacetates
(IV: R=CH₂CO₂Et; R₁=CH₂Cl; R₂=H and R=CH₂CO₂Et; R₁=H; R₂=CH₂Cl)

(a). Dry HCl gas was passed through a mixture of ethyl *m*-methoxyphenylacetate (5 g.), formalin (40%, 3 c.c.), zinc chloride (0.3 g.) and ether (25 c.c.) at room tempera-

ture for half an hour for complete saturation. When the reaction mixture warmed up, it was cooled in an ice-bath. The ethereal layer was washed with water, sodium carbonate solution (10%) and water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was fractionated: (i) unchanged material (0.5 g.), b.p. 105-110°/0.6 mm; (ii) desired compound (1.7 g.), b.p. 130-40°/0.6 mm. (Found: Cl, 14.12. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.63%). Using the same quantities of the materials but saturating it in the cold, the yield of the desired chloro compound was 1.22 g.

(b). Dry hydrogen chloride was passed through a mixture of ethyl *m*-methoxyphenylacetate (5 g.), paraformaldehyde (0.5 g.) and ether (30 c.c.) at room temperature till saturation. The reaction mixture was worked up to furnish the chloro compound (0.64 g.).

Oxidation of the Chloro-esters.—To the chloro-ester (1 g.) was added slowly a solution of $KMnO_4$ (4.8 g.) and NaOH (8 g.) in water (120 c.c.). The reaction mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 6 hours, made colorless with ethanol and filtered. The precipitated manganese dioxide was washed thoroughly with hot water. The filtrate was concentrated, acidified and extracted repeatedly with ether. After evaporation of the solvent, the gummy residue was treated with ether when a fraction went into solution leaving a white solid, m.p. 280-85°, which was crystallised three times from hot water to furnish colorless prisms of methoxyterephthalic acid (0.06 g.), m.p. 293-95°. (Found: C, 55.53; H, 4.31. Calc. for $C_9H_8O_5$: C, 55.10; H, 4.08%). The ether-soluble fraction was crystallised three times from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to afford 4-methoxyphthalic acid (0.2 g.), m.p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 55.41; H, 4.27. Calc. for $C_9H_8O_5$: C, 55.10; H, 4.08%).

3-Methoxy-6-chloromethyl- and 3-Methoxy-4-chloromethyl-benzyl Chlorides (IV: $R=R_1=CH_2Cl$; $R_2=H$ and $R=R_2=CH_2Cl$; $R_1=H$).—Dry HCl gas was passed rapidly (if the rate of flow of the gas is slow then the whole of the material will polymerise) through a mixture of *m*-methoxybenzyl chloride (28 g.), zinc chloride (2 g.), formalin (17 c.c.) and ether (100 c.c.) at room temperature for 1 hour to completely saturate it. After sometime the reaction mixture warmed up. It was worked up as before and fractionated: (i) unchanged material (5.2 g.), b.p. 80-82°/0.8 mm; (ii) the dichloro compounds (29 g.), 115-20°/0.8 mm. (Found: Cl, 34.15. $C_9H_{10}OCl_2$ requires Cl, 34.63%).

Utilising *m*-methoxybenzyl chloride (4.5 g.), formalin (2.4 c.c.), zinc chloride (0.3 g.) and ether (35 c.c.) and cooling the reaction mixture, when warmed up, the desired product (3.05 g.) was obtained. No reaction took place when paraformaldehyde was substituted for formalin, and the reaction was carried out, as described above, in an ice-bath.

Oxidation of the above mixture of the dichloro compounds (1 g.), as described before, furnished 4-methoxyphthalic acid (0.35 g.), m.p. 169-70°, and methoxyterephthalic acid (0.1 g.), m.p. 293-95°.

3-Methoxybenzene-1:6- and -1:4-diacetonitriles (IV: $R=R_1=CH_2.CN$; $R_2=H$ and $R=R_2=CH_2.CN$; $R_1=H$).—To a boiling solution of potassium cyanide (30 g.) in

a mixture of water (40 c.c.) and ethanol (120 c.c.) were added dropwise the above dichloro compounds (30 g.) in such a way that the heat of reaction kept the reaction mixture boiling. After the addition was complete, the mixture was allowed to reflux for half an hour more. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was distilled, b.p. 160-70°/0.2 mm. On redistillation it furnished pure dinitriles (16 g.), b.p. 160-62°/2 mm. (Found: N, 14.68. $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 15.05%).

3-Methoxybenzene-1:6- and -1:4-diacetic Acids (IV: $R=R_1=CH_2CO_2H$; $R_2=H$ and $R=R_2=CH_2CO_2H$; $R_1=H$).—(a). The mixture of diethyl esters (9.3 g., b.p. 155-65°/0.4 mm), prepared by refluxing the above dinitriles (12 g.), double distilled ethanol (100 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 c.c.) for 16 hours, was not completely free of nitrogen. It was refluxed with a solution of KOH (18 g.) in a mixture of water (20 c.c.) and methanol (150 c.c.). The reaction mixture was worked up to give solid dicarboxylic acids (6 g.), m.p. 148-50°, a part of which was crystallised four times from ether-benzene mixture, m.p. 158-59°. (Found: C, 59.01; H, 5.63. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.92; H, 5.35%).

(b). A mixture of the chloro-esters (IV: $R=CH_2CO_2Et$; $R_1=CH_2Cl$; $R_2=H$ and $R=CH_2CO_2Et$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CH_2Cl$; 2.25 g.), acetone (50 c.c.), potassium cyanide (1.5 g.), sodium iodide (0.2 g.) and water (2.4 c.c.) was refluxed for 20 hours. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue, after dilution with water and acidification with HCl (cold, dil.), was extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene. The organic layer was washed with water and distilled. The dry residue was refluxed with a mixture of double distilled ethanol (15 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 3 c.c.) to furnish an oil (0.85 g.) which was hydrolysed with methanol (9 c.c.), KOH (1 g.) and water (1 c.c.), as described above, to give a solid acid, m.p. 140-45°, which on crystallisation yielded a pure mixture of acids, m.p. 158-59°, the mixed m.p. of which with those described above remained undepressed.

Dimethyl 3-Methoxybenzene-1:6- and -1:4-diacetates (IV: $R=R_1=CH_2CO_2Me$; $R_2=H$ and $R=R_2=CH_2CO_2Me$; $R_1=H$).—The mixture of the above crude acids (3.8 g.) was esterified with diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (8 g.), in ethereal solution to yield the esters (4 g.), b.p. 150-52°/0.6 mm. (Found: C, 61.48; H, 6.68. $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.90; H, 6.34%).

Methyl 5-Methoxyhydrind-2-one-1- and -3-carboxylates (II: $R=H$; $R_1=CO_2Me$ and $R=CO_2Me$; $R_1=H$).—To sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (1.08 g.) under dry benzene and absolute methanol (1.46 c.c.), were added dropwise with shaking under nitrogen the dimethyl esters (4 g.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.). The reaction which started at the room temperature was completed by refluxing on a water-bath for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated enolate was dissolved in cold water. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether. On removal of organic solvent, the residue was distilled (1 g.), b.p.

150°/0.6 mm. The aqueous solution on acidification with cold dilute acetic acid furnished a material (m.p. 95-100°), which on evaporative distillation at 130-35°/1.5 mm yielded a crystalline material, m.p. 95-105°. The latter gave a deep blue colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and on fractional crystallisation from methanol gave (i) a β -keto ester (0.5 g.), m.p. 97-98° (Found: C, 65.20; H, 5.62. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.45; H, 5.45%); (ii) another less soluble β -keto ester (350 mg.), m.p. 126-27° (Found: C, 65.21; H, 5.63. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.45; H, 5.45%).

5-Methoxy-2-indanone (II: R=R₁=H).—(a). The β -keto ester (0.2 g., m.p. 97-98°) was refluxed with 20% H₂SO₄ (5 c.c.) for 4 hours under nitrogen. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water and then extracted thrice with ether. The organic layer was washed with cold saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried. The solvent was distilled and the residue was evaporatively distilled at 80-90°/1.5 mm to furnish a crystalline ketone (0.12 g.), m.p. 75-80°. The methoxy-indanone, thus obtained, developed in presence of air a brown colour within a very short time. It developed a deep blue colour, characteristic of β -indanone system (Moore and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*) with H₂SO₄ (conc.) containing a trace of an oxidising agent. The *semicarbazone* (0.1 g.), m.p. 218-19°, obtained from the above ketone (0.1 g.), was crystallised three times from methanol, m.p. 226-27°. (Found: N, 19.40. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 19.17%).

The other isomeric β -keto ester furnished the same ketone, m.p. 75-80°, on similar hydrolysis.

(b). The acids (IV: R=R₁=CH₂.CO₂H; R₂=H and R=R₂=CH₂.CO₂H; R₁=H; 0.4 g.) were well mixed with dry lead carbonate (0.4 g.) in a sublimation tube. The air was displaced with nitrogen and the tube was introduced in a heating bath maintained at 300-305°. After 10 minutes a colorless oil came over. It solidified after some time, m.p. 75-80°. It was characterised through its semicarbazone.

The β -keto ester (200 mg., m.p. 97-98°) was oxidised as before to yield 4-methoxyphthalic acid (0.04 g.), m.p. 169-70°.

Attempted Methylation of the β -Keto Ester.—To the enolate, prepared from the β -keto ester (0.88 g.), m.p. 97-98°, sodium dust (0.1 g.), dry benzene (20 c.c.), under nitrogen, was added methyl iodide (2 c.c.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hours and diluted with water. The aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether and the combined extract was washed with aqueous NaOH solution (5%) and water, and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the residue (0.75 g.) was hydrolysed as before to yield an oil (0.3 g.), evaporatively distilling at 100°/0.2 mm. The oil was converted into the semicarbazone, m.p. 215-17°, which on five crystallisations from dilute methanol afforded a material in 0.017 g. yield, m.p. 238-39°. The analysis (Found: N, 14.47%) definitely indicated that it was neither pure nor homogeneous.

Attempted Mannich-Robinson Reaction.—(a). The reaction of methiodide of 1-diethylamino-3-butanone (0.53 g. of base) in benzene (8 c.c.) with 5-methoxy-2-indanone (0.6 g.) in methanolic sodium methoxide (5 c.c., 0.136 g. of Na) under nitrogen furnished only a polymerised product.

(b). A methanolic solution of the enolate of the β -keto ester, m.p. 97-98° (0.41 g; Na, 0.042 g.) was allowed to react with the methiodide (0.28 g. of base) in methanol. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 20 hours, refluxed for one hour and then worked up to furnish an oil (0.6 g); λ_{max} 280 m μ . The latter on treatment with glacial acetic acid and HCl gave an oil (0.02 g.), evaporatively distilling at 160°/0.2 mm, which failed to furnish a semicarbazone.

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